

DESCRIPTION OF SOIL UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF CHEMICAL POLLUTION AND CHANGES TO THE SOIL

¹Jabbarov Zafarjon Abdukarimovich, ²Fakhrutdinova Mashkura Fazliddinovna, ³Imomov Otamurod Normamatovich

¹National university of Uzbekistan, Faculty Biology, Department of Soil science d.b.s., professor

²National university of Uzbekistan, Faculty Biology, Department of Soil science c.b.s., docent

³National university of Uzbekistan, Faculty Biology, Department of Soil science doctorate

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11379270>

Annotation. Chemical degradation of soils in industrial areas and changes in their indicators are the most common form of the negative effect of polluting industrial waste sources on the soil. This threatens our limited soil resource as it tends to reduce the quality of the soil. Therefore, it is necessary to limit the means that destroy the soil chemically. Analysis of soil indicators, assessment of changes in chemical degradation of soil, prevention of some pollution, evaluation of soil health quality and fertility, by studying it is considered effective. One of the causes of chemical soil degradation is soil pollution, mainly diffuse pollutants (wind, water, industrial air), the composition of industrial wastewater, such degrading factors (ash elements, household industrial waste, heavy metals) of the soil, chemical fertilizers and helps to use pesticides. Chemically degraded soils can be prevented from becoming irreversible in many cases by analyzing soil indicators and restoring fertility. In order to maintain soil health, quality and productivity, it helps to reclamation and prevent chemical degradation of chemically degraded soils and agricultural stability.

Key words: soil indicator, diffusion pollution, local pollution, soil quality, soil health, soil fertility.

Аннотация. Химическая деградация почв промышленных территорий и изменение их показателей являются наиболее распространенной формой негативного воздействия на почву источников загрязнения промышленных отходов. Это угрожает нашим ограниченными почвенным ресурсам, поскольку приводит к снижению качества почвы. Поэтому необходимо ограничить средства, химически разрушающие почву. анализ показателей почвы, оценка изменений химической деградации почвы, предотвращение некоторых загрязнений, оценка состояния здоровья и плодородия почвы, путем ее изучения считается эффективным. Одной из причин химической деградации почв является загрязнение почвы, преимущественно диффузными загрязнителями (ветер, вода, промышленный воздух), составом промышленных сточных вод, такими деградирующими факторами (зольные элементы, бытовые промышленные отходы, тяжелые металлы) почвы, химическими удобрениями помогает использовать пестициды. Во многих случаях можно предотвратить необратимое развитие химически деградированных почв путем анализа показателей почвы и восстановления плодородия. Для поддержания здоровья, качества и продуктивности почвы он помогает мелиорировать и предотвращать химическую деградацию химически деградированных почв и стабильность сельского хозяйства.

Ключевые слова: почвенный индикатор, диффузное загрязнение, локальное загрязнение, качество почвы, здоровье почвы, плодородие почвы.

Annotatsiya. Sanoat hududlaridagi tuproqlarning kimyoviy jihatdan degridatsiyalanishi va ularning indikator ko`rsatkichlarini o`zgarishi ifloslantiruvchi sanoat chiqindi manbaalarini tuproqqa ta`sirining salbiy natijasidagi eng keng tarqalgan shaklidir. Bu cheklangan tuproq

resursimizga xavf tug'diradi, chunki u tuproqning sifatiga undan kamroq foydalanishga moyil bo'ladi. Shunday ekan tuproqlarni kimyoviy yo'l bilan buzadigan vositalarni cheklashni taqozo etadi. tuproq indikatorlarini tahlil qilish tuproqning kimyoviy degradatsiyasining ba'zi ifloslanishni oldini olish tuproq soqg'omligi sifati va unumdroligini baholash orqali o'rganish orqali o'zgarishlarini baholash samarali hisoblnadi. Tuproqni kimyoviy jihatdan degradatsiyalash sabablaridan biri tuproqning ifloslanishi asosan diffuz ifloslanitiruvchilar (shamol, suv, sanoat havosi) Sanoat oqava suvlarining tarkibi, bunday degradatsiylovchi faktorlar (kul elementlar, maishiy sanoat chiqindilari, og'ir metallar) tuproqning, kimyoviy o'g'itlarni qo'llash va pestitsidlardan foydalanishga yordam beradi. Tuproqni indikatorlari qiyoslash orqali tahlil qilish va unumdorligini tiklash orqali kimyoviy degradatsiyaga uchragan tuproqlar ko'p hollarda qaytarib bo'lmaydigan holatga kelishi bo'lishi mumkin holatdan saqlaydi. Tuproq sog'omligi, sifati va unumdorligi saqlash uchun kimyoviy degradatsiya uchragan tuproqlarning melioratsiya qilishga va kimyoviy degradatsiyasini oldini olishga va qishloq xo'jaligi barqarorligiga yordam beradi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** diffuzion ifloslanish, lokal ifloslanish, tuproq sifati, tuproq sog'omligi, tuproq unumdorligi.*

INTRADUCTION. To date, the delivery of ecologically clean products in terms of food security in agriculture directly depends on the health and productivity of the soil. For researchers in the field of soil science, agriculture has become essential to understand. Identifying the main sources and factors affecting the occurrence of chemical degradation spread in the territory of irrigated lands in our republic, the type of chemical pollution, the physical and chemical biological properties of soils and the effect on soil fertility, the selection of suitable indicators that improve the condition, the development of chemical degradation indicators and the approach of classification through modern methods, the importance of each indicator in the classification of changes in indicators, and the study of indicators are considered effective. Comprehensive measures aimed at restoring soil fertility and their effective use being implemented. In the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2026, "...increasing soil fertility and the productivity of agricultural crops, further improving the land reclamation status of irrigated lands, expanding the production of environmentally friendly products, using land resources effectively and rationally important tasks on use" are defined. In this regard, it is important to determine the properties of chemically degraded soils according to the areas of pollution and soil genetic layers, to identify and classify the types of suitable indicators for them.

The lands of our republic make up 9.6% of the total land fund, the main agricultural crops are grown on these irrigated lands, but the soil fertility of these lands is not normal. As a result of chemical pollution, a certain part of the soil is degraded, its productivity decreases, soil quality and health condition deteriorates, the state of soil health changes, its physical chemical biological indicator properties change, and it is no longer used in agriculture as a result of the impact on soils and the environment. The transition to invalid status is increasing. Understanding Soil health, quality, fertility indicators one of the best ways to use soil effectively is to identify and manage soil indicators, which will allow you to understand how to manage your soil and use soil indicator parameters to improve soil health productivity and quality.

RESEARCH METHODS AND MATERIALS. Soil respiration, bacterial and actinobacterial colonies, pH environment [1-3], bacteriological composition [4-6], as well as indicators of soil color, granularity and structure are effective in assessing soil quality [7-8].

Climate change should also be taken into account when assessing soil quality [9]. There are different programs that monitor soil conditions, [Bunemann et al. 2018] reviewed a number of international programs and found that the most common indicators are indicators through total or organic carbon, pH, available phosphorus, water retention, soil density. Several relatively similar programs of the countries of Australia, Europe, and New Zealand have been studied.

Statistical methods such as principal component analysis are often used as sampling methods [Lilburne et al. 2004]. Data collected from the soil quality monitoring program is not only the basis for regional and national interstate reporting [Drewry et al. 2021; MFE & Stats N Z 2021, 2018], [Stevenson and Parfitt et al 2015]. Identify the parameters that best differentiate soil use, including pH environment, bacteriological composition, total carbon, total N, P (phosphorus), soil density and texture. Pochvy klassifikatsiya khimicheskikh veshchestv dlya kontrolya zagryazneniya: Izdatelstvo standartov 1983. GOST 17.4.4.02–84 Pochvy. Methods of preparation and preparation of probes for chemical and biological analysis. - M. : Izdatelstvo standartov, 1984. – 4 p., GOST 26213-91 Soil. Methody opredeleniya organicheskogo veshchestva. - M. : Izdatelstvo standartov, 1991. – 8 p., GOST 28168–89 Pochvy. Otkor probe. - M. : Izdatelstvo standartov, 1989. – 4 p., GOST ISO: 22030-2009, 2010;

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. Measures to improve chemically degraded soils are mainly to create a good soil environment, to fight against chemical degradation, to dispose of soil waste from the soil, to reduce soil pollution and improve aeration, to soften the soil, to mix it, to maintain water moisture, to increase moisture in arid soil, to control the temperature of the soil surface. Cultivation of soil for various purposes, such as leveling, application of fertilizers to the root zone, feeding and mixing, leads to significant changes in soil properties (Nunes et al., 2018; Çelik et al., 2021; Anonymous, 2022) . Along with this, natural factors such as tillage, irrigation, retention of heavy metals in the soil, household industrial waste and improper application of fertilizers and agricultural practices, soil structure. under the influence of chemical degradation factors, such as soil moisture, pH, amount of organic matter and biological activity, can cause significant changes in the chemical and biological properties of the soil (Vallejo et al., 2012). Tillage is an important part of the production system, agricultural characteristics that significantly change the soil physical properties, often temporarily (Mondal et al., 2020). In conventional tillage, the post-harvest seed bed is used to prepare and bury waste on the surface, usually at a depth of 25-30 cm. The soil is plowed deep with a mold plow and plowed in reverse. However, in soil conservation applications, the soil is less disturbed (e.g., <10 cm deep with discs or shallow, no-turning, harrowing. tillage) or no-disturbance and direct harvesting. After planting, it is applied to the surface (Morris et al., 2010). Reducing tillage and minimal mixing, the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil are highly variable. Reducing tillage can alleviate soil compaction damage (Jabro et al., 2009., Deubel et al. al., 2011). In areas where chemically degraded soils are conventionally cultivated depending on the degree of degradation, the soil is not tilled for a long time, that is, if the soil is not mechanically turned, the soil-plant system begins to reach a new state of physical balance over time and its functionality increases. and the indicator results in a positive change and soil health and quality improves, soil fertility functionality works. Therefore, long-term zero tillage, physical indicators of its structure and pore network, and therefore its volume, weight, aggregate, the basic physical properties of the soil, such as soil stability and water retention capacity, improve the parameters and organic soil in the soil. increases carbon content (Mondal et al., 2020). Over time, aggregates in chemically degraded soil are broken down by tillage. Soil resistance to the corrosive effects of water and wind decreases, and wind and soil erosion are

accelerated by water flow. In chemically degraded soils, tillage wastes are buried in the soil, acting as a protective layer on the surface of the soil. Since it is buried, the surface may be exposed to rain or raindrops. moving against the wind and carrying soil particles causes it to remain vulnerable. Accumulation of debris on the surface When no debris is left, it is broken down by raindrops and dispersed weak aggregates cause clogging of pores in the soil and eventually a crust forms on the surface of the soil in the form of a thin coating. This prevents water from seeping into the soil profile. (Anonymous, 2022). Weight, porosity and water holding capacity (Chelik et

al., 2021) Physical properties, beneficial nutrient status such as pH and electrical conductivity, biological properties such as chemical and organic matter, soil enzymes and beneficial soil organisms affects the quality of the soil, which is used as an indicator of the health quality of the soil. Tillage, the above-mentioned features can have a negative effect on many people. The positive effect of reducing density on soil quality, according to research

findings, the deterioration of soil quality Conflicting results have also been reported to show why this might be the case. Failure to turn the soil over can cause compaction at the soil surface, causing nutrients to accumulate at near depths where they can be easily removed by runoff. Therefore, it is said that it may pose a threat to surface water (Chelik et al., 2020; Chelik et al., 2021). In the world community, the indicator of soil health is directly related to soil fertility and is divided into physical, chemical and biological groups. There are many indicators of soil health, including organic matter content, quality-related properties, organic matter (OM) and fractional carbon sources (Schon NL, Fraser PM, Mackay AD 2022). Organic derivatives (humins, fulvins, humic acids), enzyme activity oxidoreductase groups, cofermentase groups, amidase (urease), phosphatase, invertase, catalase are used as indicators of soil health. It was found that the pesticides accumulated in the irrigated soils change chemically depending on the soil quality indicators. As a result of oxidation-reduction processes, nitrification, denitrification, ammonification, sulphification, and the processes of combinations of enzymes with soils, it is possible to ensure a positive effect on the dynamics of the movement of nutrients in improving the health of the soil by controlling these indicators. Factors leading to chemical degradation are characteristic of other regions of Uzbekistan: arid climate, mineralization of underground water, specific geomorphological and lithological conditions due to proximity to the surface of the earth, and soil formation under the influence of human activity, its properties, physical, chemical and biological activity is expressed by improving indicator parameters [Jabbarov Z.A., Imomov O.N., Nomozov U.M. 2023]. During land use in agriculture, physical, chemical and biological indicators are used to determine the quality of soils. The soil indicators developed by scientists in these scientific studies are important in improving soil health.

CONCLUSIONS, SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS. The types and importance of indicators showing the health of soils in the world were analyzed in terms of studying the influence of the indicators of the role functions in the soil. These are foreign countries such as New Zealand, New York, Columbia, Sweden, Pennsylvania, Vermont and Maryland. development of recommendations and their practical applications were studied. From this point of

view, it is important to study soil health indicators that show the health of the soil of Uzbekistan, including soil environmental relations, pollution conditions, land reclamation status in terms of salinity, the influence of soil and water dynamics, soil The quantitative share of organic matter requires proper study of soil health indicators in order to maintain and improve the quantitative content of nutrients. Currently, these soil indicators are being carried out together with scientific research. It is planned to provide this information for the use of researchers who are doing scientific research in soil science.

REFERENCES

1. Bünemann EK, Bongiorno G, Bai Z, Creamer RE, De Deyn G, de Goede R, Fleskens L, Geissen V, Kuyper TW, Mäder P, et al. Soil quality - a critical review. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 120: 105–125. 2018.
2. Parfitt R.L, Stevenson B A, Ross C, Fraser S. Changes in pH, bicarbonate-extractable P, carbon and nitrogen over 5 to 30 years for soils under pasture. *New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research* 57, 216–227. 2014.
3. Schon NL, Fraser PM, Mackay AD, Earthworms for inclusion as an indicator of soil biological health in New Zealand pastures. *New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research*, DOI: 10.1080/00288233, 2022.
4. Jabbarov Z.A., Imomov O.N., Nomozov U.M., "Effect of Improvement Drug on Chemical Degradation of Soils" *International Journal of Biological Engineering and Agriculture* ISSN:2833-5376 Volum e 2 | No. 10 | Oct -5, Pages 3-5.,2023.
5. Çelik, İ., Gunal, H., Acar, M., Acir, N., Bereket Barut, Z., Budak, M., (2020). Evaluating the long-term effects of tillage systems on soil structural quality using visual assessment and classical methods. *Soil Use and Management* 36, 223–239. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12554>
6. Anonymous, (2022). Frequent tillage and its impact on soil quality Access address: <https://crops.extension.iastate.edu/encyclopedia/frequent-tillage-and-its-impact-soil-quality> (Access date: 03.09.2022).
7. Jabro, J. D., Sainju, W. M., Stevens, W. B., Lenssen, A. W., Evans, R. G. (2009). Long-term tillage influences on soil physical properties under dryland conditions in northeastern Montana. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science* 55(6): 633-640. Carbon content, and plant root response. *Land Degradation & Development*, 31(5): 557-567.
- 8n . Mondal, S., Chakraborty, D., Bandyopadhyay, K., Aggarwal, P., Rana, D. S. (2020). Global analysis of the impact of zero-tillage on soil physical condition, organic 139-247.
9. Morris, N. L., Miller, P. C. H., Orson, J. H., Froud-Williams, R. J. (2010). The adoption of non-inversion tillage systems in the United Kingdom and the agronomic impact on soil, crops and the environment—A review. *Soil and Tillage Research* 108(1-2): 1-15.
10. Nunes, M. R., Karlen, D. L., Veum, K. S., Moorman, T. B., Cambardella, C. A. (2020). Biological soil health indicators respond to tillage intensity: A US meta-analysis. *Geoderma* 369:114335.
11. Vallejo, V. E., Arbeli, Z., Terán, W., Lorenz, N., Dick, R. P., Roldan, F. (2012). Effect of land management and *Prosopis juliflora* (Sw.) DC trees on soil microbial community and enzymatic activities in intensive silvopastoral systems of Colombia. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment* 150: 139-148.